

**COMPUTER ASSISTED INSTRUCTION: ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN TEACHING
SCIENCE**

LORNA P. DUNKEN

Master Teacher I

Department of Education – SDO Bataan

2019

INTRODUCTION

The basic aim of instructional research is to find how to develop an instructional environment that can provide easier learning and upper level competence among the learners in a short time and at less expense and endeavour. The living styles of the people not only affect their learning styles but also determine how they may improve the capacity to learn given the resources at hand. Advances in technologies have greatly simplified the learning process and even shortened the differences between the field of education and other disciplines. The development and prevalence of computer technologies in every aspect of study provides not only speed and economy but also visual and sound opportunity.

According to Murray (2013), digital literacy is one of those “technologies in the classroom” buzzwords floated by experts as being granular to 21st century students. It is everywhere, on everyone’s tongue, but figuring what it really means is daunting. Literacy is simply the ability to read and write. But digital literacy is more than that. It needs to focus in achieving the goals of technologies in the classroom.

The use of computers in classroom instructions has become so popular and eased up the instruction process, especially to those who are well adept in the computer-assisted instructions (CAI). The rising trend in computer-aided education has also helped the learners develop their raw knowledge in modern technology and further arose their interest in it.

These technological developments and advances, along with new computer products and applications, are taking its toll on the traditional education method. The need to step with the changing technology becomes imperative and soon, the integration of technology in the curriculum became inevitable. And everything in the field of education has become technology-dependent with some even becoming technology-based.

Even instructional materials have taken a new look. Education practitioners have found an ally in technology. Preparation of teaching materials has been much easier with the use of the modern technology. The computerization of instructional materials is the new trend in education. Although it entails additional expenses to the teachers, it is undoubtedly much preferred because of the various programs and applications available which put teaching to a new level of awareness and interest. The use of computer-based instructional materials greatly help in making the class topics clearer and more lasting by making the abstract topics concrete.

The integration of technology into educational systems has begun to embrace the new approaches towards transforming traditional learning environments into active learning through questions, collaboration and discussions (Keengwe, Onchwari and Oigara, 2014). Technology is fast becoming a part of the instructional method and its importance cannot be discounted, considering the breadth by which it has affected the young learners today. It is therefore imperative among the teachers to highlight the benefits and perceptions of technology in their attempt to capture learners' attentions.

These technological advances can make teaching and learning easier and better, science education can very well benefit from it. Since some concepts of Science are quite abstract, presenting them through the computer languages and applications which can make understanding of these concepts much acceptable to the learners. Presenting difficult science concepts to the students through the traditional methods of education can really be taxing to the teacher and confusing to the learners. There has to be an alternative approach to education which will trigger the consciousness and willingness of the learners to fully understand what is being taught. The developments in the technology bring new learning and teaching opportunities. (Keengwe 2014).

The advent of computers proved their position in education and instructions. And it is for these reasons that the researcher would like to establish the efficiency of employing computer-aided medium of instruction in teaching Science which is one of the components in science for elementary learners, specifically Grade 6 pupils.

Since the primary aim of teaching is to impart knowledge to the learners, teachers need to be innovative in presenting lessons in such a way that the interest of the learners can be positively triggered. Lessons need not be presented in ways which can confuse the inquisitive minds of the children. And what better way to address the issue than to use a method which best interest them. With the young learners' minds greatly fixated on computers, teachers should take advantage of such fixation to present lessons and capture the interest of the learners without even trying much to catch their attention. This may lessen the traditional need to motivate the learners toward a particular topic since the mere use of modern technology is enough motivation for them.

It is in this context that the researcher was prompted to conduct this study.

METHODOLOGY

The study aimed to determine the efficiency of Computer Assisted Medium of Instruction in Teaching Science to Grade 6 pupils. The descriptive correlational method was utilized to achieve this purpose.

According to Calderon et al. (2012) descriptive methods of research involves the description, recording, analysis and interpretation of the present nature, composition or processes of phenomena, which focuses on prevailing conditions, or how a person, group or thing behaves or functions in the present. It often involves some type of comparison or contrast. In other words, descriptive research maybe defined as a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, trends and cause effect relationships and then making adequate and accurate interpretation about such data with or without the aid of statistical methods.

On the other hand, Krishnaswamy, Sivakumar and Mathirajan (2009) defined descriptive research as fact-finding with adequate interpretation. The descriptive method is something more and beyond just data gathering; the latter is not reflective thinking or research. The true meaning of the data collected should be reported from the point of view of the objectives and the basic assumption of the project under way. This follows logically after careful classification of data. Facts obtained may' be accurate expressions

of central tendency, or deviation, or of correlation; but the report is not research unless discussion of those data is not carried up to the level of interpretations. Data are subject to the thinking process in terms of ordered reasoning.

Furthermore, Aggarwal (2008) emphasized that descriptive research is devoted to the gathering of information about prevailing conditions or situations for the purpose of description and interpretation. This type of research method is not simply amassing and tabulating facts but includes proper analyses, interpretation, comparisons, identification of trends and relationships.

Moreover, Picciano (2015), described that correlational research is used to explore co-varying relationships between two or more variables. A simple definition of a co-varying relationship is as one variable changes so does the other variable(s). The purpose of correlational research is to identify variables that relate to one each, to make predictions of one variable from another and to examine possible cause and effect relationships between one variable and another.

On the other hand, Friedman & Wyatt (2006), described that correlational studies are different from comparative studies in that the evaluator does not control the allocation of subjects into comparison groups or assignment of the intervention to specific groups. Instead, the evaluator defines a set of variables including an outcome of interest then tests for hypothesized relations among these variables. The outcome is known as the dependent variable and the variables being tested for association are the independent variables. Correlational studies are similar to comparative studies in that they take on an objectivist view where the variables can be defined, measured and analyzed for the

presence of hypothesized relations. As such, correlational studies face the same challenges as comparative studies in terms of their internal and external validity. Of particular importance are the issues of design choices, selection bias, confounders, and reporting consistency.

RESULTS

Table 2

Profile of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Computer Literacy

Computer Literacy	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Basic Computer Knowledge	3.65	0.95	Advanced
Internet Literacy	3.74	0.87	Advanced
Computer Aided Instruction Literacy Training-Workshop	3.61	1.05	Advanced
Microsoft Office	3.50	1.08	Advanced
Google Apps	3.57	1.00	Advanced
Programming	3.57	1.00	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.61	0.54	Advanced

Legend:

Scale	Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating
5	4.20 – 5.00	Expert
4	3.40 – 4.19	Advanced
3	2.60 – 3.39	Intermediate
2	1.80 – 2.59	Beginner
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Sure

Table 2 displays the profile of the teacher – respondents in terms of computer literacy.

The table discloses that the respondents’ literacy obtained the highest mean of 3.74 described as advanced. It was followed by their basic computer knowledge with a mean of 3.65 with its descriptive rating as advanced. The lowest mean was registered on Microsoft office with a mean of 3.5 but still descriptive by rated as advanced.

These findings tend to imply that the respondents professionally upgraded themselves in terms of computer skills. It could be assumed that they had attended several seminars on computer – related topics.

Table 3

Teachers’ Competence in Computer Education in Terms of Operating System

Operating System	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Knows out the plan how to install Operating System	3.56	1.13	Advanced
Knows the meaning of screen icons	3.72	0.94	Advanced
Use the mouse and keyboard.	3.80	1.14	Advanced
Sets up device driver.	3.81	1.05	Advanced
Configure network requirement.	3.63	0.96	Advanced
Install application software.	3.57	1.14	Advanced
Understands antivirus, firewall and malware.	3.61	1.12	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.67	0.68	Advanced

Table 3 presents teachers' competence in computer education in terms of operating system. As shown on the table, most of the teacher-respondents competence in computer education in terms of operating system was on how to set up device driver with the highest weighted mean of 3.81, followed by identifying the meaning of screen icons with 3.72 as the weighted mean and the least competence was posted on how to install operating system with 3.56 weighted mean. In general, results revealed that the respondents' competence in computer education in terms of operating system was advanced with 3.67 as the composite mean.

These findings seem to imply that the respondents are knowledgeable when it comes to operating system. It could be inferred that in the teaching process teacher-respondents' are updated with regards to the present curriculum. It could also be assumed that teacher-respondents' knowledge in operating system help them specifically on troubleshooting in order to resolve technical problems to operate computer.

Table 4

Teachers' Competence in Computer Education in Terms of Word Processing, Desktop Publishing Software and Multimedia

Word Processing, Desktop Publishing Software, Multimedia	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Understand how a word processor can be used.	3.41	1.09	Advanced
Uses simple editing (e.g. bold, centering).	3.70	0.94	Advanced
Uses a spellchecker.	3.80	1.14	Advanced

Imports texts and images into word processed document.	3.81	1.05	Advanced
Lays out text and pictures	3.61	0.98	Advanced
Install application software.	3.59	1.16	Advanced
Publishes work using multimedia / hypermedia.	3.61	1.12	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.65	0.69	Advanced

Table 4 displays the teachers' competence in computer education in terms of word processing, desktop publishing software and multimedia.

As shown on the table, imports texts and images into word processed document was the highest competence of the respondents with a weighted mean of 3.81 and the least competency was on how a word processor can be used with 3.41 weighted mean. However, the totality of the teacher-respondents' competence in computer education in terms of word processing, desktop publishing software and multimedia was advanced.

The obtained results seem to indicate that most of the respondents availed the trainings on computer education in terms of word processing, desktop publishing software and multimedia. Perhaps, the acquired competencies and skills along these areas were products of their attendance and trainings they attended.

Table 5

Teachers' Competence in Computer Education in Terms of Database

Database	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
----------	------	----	--------------------

Understands how a database can be used.	3.35	1.14	Intermediate
Sets up a database.	3.43	1.13	Advanced
Edits fields in the database.	3.52	1.19	Advanced
Enters and coverts data in the database.	3.28	1.16	Advanced
Creates different layout in the data entry / reports.	3.41	1.19	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.40	0.79	Advanced

Table 5 presents teachers' competence in computer education in terms of database.

As shown on the table, the first three highest weighted means were recorded on indicators **edits fields in the database** with 3.52 as its weighted mean, **sets up a database** with 3.43 weighted mean and **creates different layout in the data entry/reports** with 3.41 weighted mean.

These results tend to suggest that the teacher-respondents were knowledgeable on the use of database. Likewise, teacher-respondents perhaps are sold to the importance of database in completing the required forms like pupils and school-data. Hence, they made efforts to be on the advanced level in terms of database.

Table 6

Teachers' Competence in Computer Education in Terms of Spreadsheets and Simulations

Spreadsheets and Simulations	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Understands how a spreadsheet can be used.	3.50	1.11	Advanced
Sets up datasheet.	3.52	1.06	Advanced
Uses spreadsheet to prepare the performance rating.	3.72	1.02	Advanced
Uses spreadsheet to produce reports.	3.70	1.09	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.61	0.63	Advanced

Table 6 displays the teachers' competence in computer education in terms of spreadsheets and simulations. As seen on the table, the first three highest weighted means were recorded on indicators **uses spreadsheet to prepare the performance rating** with 3.72 as its weighted mean, uses spreadsheet to produce reports with 3.70 as weighted mean and set up datasheet with 3.52 weighted mean.

The obtained result seems to indicate that respondents are computer literate in using spreadsheets and simulation. It implies that spreadsheets are the friendliest software of the respondents in terms of computing grades and completing the school forms needed for checking and submission.

Table 7

Teachers' Competence in Computer Education in Terms of Painting and Drawing

Painting / Drawing	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
---------------------------	-------------	-----------	---------------------------

Understands how a painting package can be used.	3.41	1.09	Advanced
Uses range of tools (e.g. brush, color, chart, etc.)	3.37	1.00	Intermediate
Understands how a drawing package can help you.	3.44	1.14	Advanced
Understands the difference between drawing and painting.	3.72	1.14	Advanced
Exports images / text between painting or drawing.	3.50	1.11	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.49	0.69	Advanced

Table 7 shows the teachers' competence in computer education in terms of painting and drawing.

As reflected on the table, the teachers were revealed to understand the difference between drawing and painting by the highest weighted mean with 3.72. This was followed by their competence in exports images / text between painting or drawing with 3.50 as weighted mean. However, teachers' least competence was recorded on the use of range of tools (e.g. brush, color, chart, etc.) with a weighted mean of 3.41.

However, the figure discloses that the composite weighted mean with 3.49 and descriptive rating as advance implicates that teacher-respondents are competent on the said computer education as painting and drawing, because it reveals that even for pupils it was very basic knowledge in the field of computer technology.

Table 8

Teachers' Competence in Computer Education in Terms of Use of Devices

Using Devices	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Uses digital camera.	3.52	1.19	Advanced
Uses printer.	3.28	1.16	Intermediate
Uses digital projector.	3.41	1.19	Advanced
Uses scanner for importing images.	3.59	1.16	Advanced
Uses CD-ROM	3.61	1.12	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.48	0.77	Advanced

Table 8 displays the teachers' competence in computer education in terms of use of devices.

As shown on the table, the first three highest weighted means were recorded on indicators **uses of CD-ROM** with 3.61 as its weighted mean, **uses scanner for importing images** with 3.59 as weighted mean and **uses of digital camera** with 3.52 weighted mean.

The obtained results seem to indicate that respondents are familiar with the use of devices as it is needed in the present curriculum stating that teachers must be globally competitive in terms of computer education especially we are in the 21st century.

Table 9

Teachers' Competence in Computer Education in Terms of Internet Usage

Using Internet	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Understands the use of Internet Browser.	3.44	1.14	Advanced
Uses search engine to find information.	3.72	1.14	Advanced
Downloads information from the internet.	3.81	1.05	Advanced
Uses internet for self-directing learning.	3.61	0.98	Advanced
Publishes work on the Internet through Wiki and / or Weblog.	3.57	1.14	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.63	0.74	Advanced

Table 9 displays teachers' competence in computer education in terms of internet usage.

As seen on the table, the first three highest weighted means were recorded on **downloads information from the internet** with 3.81 as weighted mean, **uses search engine to find information** with 3.72 as weighted mean and **uses internet for self-directing learning** with 3.61 weighted mean.

The obtained results tend to imply that the teachers are knowledgeable on internet usage. This could be perhaps attributed to their positive attitudes on the use of internet in CAI. It could be assumed that majority of the teachers do not only enjoy the use of internet but they found the usage of it very beneficial in doing their teaching jobs and other inherent jobs like preparing required reports and documents.

Table 10

Teachers' Competence in Computer Education in Terms of E-mail Usage

Using E-mail	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Understands how the E-mail can be used.	3.52	1.19	Advanced
Sends and receives E-mail.	3.28	1.16	Intermediate
Attach files to outgoing E-mail.	3.41	1.19	Advanced
Saves files attached to incoming E-mail.	3.65	1.03	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.46	0.66	Advanced

Table 10 displays teachers' competence in computer education in terms of e-mail usage.

As shown on the table, the first three highest weighted means were recorded on **saves files attached to incoming e-mail** with a weighted mean of 3.65, **understands how the E-mail can be used** with a weighted mean of 3.52 and **attach files to outgoing E-mail** with 3.41 weighted mean.

The results of the study tend to reveal that teachers have a high level of knowledge using E-mail due to the fully maximized capability, functions and features of using E-mail in our everyday life and use it as way of communication process.

The lowest weighted mean of 3.28 with its descriptive rating as immediate is obtained by indicator **sends and receives e-mail**. This finding could perhaps be attributed to the fact that DepED Memoranda are not sent directly to them but to their administrators. It could also be possible that the use of smart cell-phone replaced the use of e-mail.

Table 11**Profile of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Their Level of Experience in Teaching Science**

Experience in Teaching Science	Mean	SD	Descriptive rating
Inspiring pupils to learn Science.	3.52	1.19	Moderate Extent
Explaining Science concepts or principles by doing Physics experiments	3.28	1.16	Low Extent
Providing challenging tasks for the highest achieving students	3.41	1.19	Moderate Extent
Adapting CAI to engage pupils' interest.	3.76	0.95	Moderate Extent
Helping pupils appreciate the value of CAI in learning Science.	3.50	1.18	Moderate Extent
Assessing pupils' comprehension in Science.	3.69	0.89	Moderate Extent
Improving the understanding of struggling pupils.	3.78	1.02	Moderate Extent
Making Science relevant to pupils.	3.52	1.14	Moderate Extent
Developing pupils' higher-order thinking skills	3.59	1.16	Moderate Extent
Teaching Science using Computer Assisted Medium of Instruction (CAI)	3.61	1.12	Moderate Extent
Composite Mean	3.56	0.45	Moderate Extent

Legend:

Scale

Rating Scale

Descriptive Rating

5	4.20 – 5.00	High Extent
4	3.40 – 4.19	Moderate Extent
3	2.60 – 3.39	Low Extent
2	1.80 – 2.59	Very Low Extent
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not At All

Table 11 displays the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of their experience in teaching Science.

As could be gleaned, the table reflects that indicators **improving the understanding of struggling pupils** has the highest weighted mean of 3.78, followed by indicator **adapting CAI to engage pupils' interest** with 3.76 weighted mean, and followed by **assessing pupils' comprehension in Science** with 3.69 weighted mean.

The results of the study tend to reveal that teacher – respondents experienced teaching Science on a moderate extent. As part of their experience, findings revealed that **explaining science concepts or principles by doing Physics experiments** obtained 3.28 weighted mean described as low extent.

The composite mean result of 3.56 on experience in teaching science tend to imply that most teacher –respondents is moderately capable of teaching science and still can level up the teaching learning experience through available tools in integrating computer assisted instruction CAI.

Table 12

Experience of the Teachers in Teaching Science Using the Computer Aided Instructions

Knowledge in Teaching Science Using CAI	Mean	SD	Descriptive rating
Science - Distance, time, Speed	3.81	1.05	Somewhat Prepared
Science – Velocity	3.61	0.98	Somewhat Prepared
Science - Kinetic Energy	3.67	1.06	Somewhat Prepared
Science - Manipulate Physics Problems	3.44	1.06	Somewhat Prepared
Science - Do scientific procedures and experiments	3.78	1.09	Somewhat Prepared
Composite Mean	3.66	0.50	Somewhat Prepared

Legend:

Scale	Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very well prepared
4	3.40 – 4.19	Somewhat Prepared
3	2.60 – 3.39	Not well Prepared
2	1.80 – 2.59	I do not teach these topics
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not At All

Table 12 displays the experience of the teachers in teaching Science using the computer aided instructions.

As could be gleaned, the table reflects that indicator **science-distance, time, speed** has the highest weighted mean 3.81, followed by indicator **science - do scientific procedures and experiments** with 3.78 weighted mean.

The lowest weighted mean which is 3.44 is obtained by indicator **science - manipulate physics problems**.

The composite mean of 3.66 using computer assisted instruction which is “somewhat prepared” in its descriptive equivalent tends to imply that the teacher-respondents need further support to enhance their understanding and possess skills needed in using CAI in manipulating Physics problems.

Table 13

Profile of the Pupils in Terms of Computer Literacy

Computer Literacy	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Basic Computer Knowledge	3.90	1.14	Advanced
Word Processing	3.93	2.32	Advanced
Spreadsheet	3.75	1.23	Advanced
PowerPoint	3.74	0.94	Advanced
Publisher	3.37	0.98	Intermediate
Google Apps	3.31	0.97	Intermediate
Video Games	3.45	1.05	Advanced
Painting/Drawing	3.76	0.90	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.65	0.56	Advanced

Legend:

Scale	Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating
5	4.20 – 5.00	Expert
4	3.40 – 4.19	Advanced

3	2.60 – 3.39	Intermediate
2	1.80 – 2.59	Beginner
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Sure

Table 13 displays the profile of the pupils in terms of computer literacy.

As could be gleaned, the table reflects that indicator **word processing** has the highest weighted mean result 3.93, followed by **basic computer knowledge** with weighted mean of 3.90.

Results as reflected in the table tends to imply that pupils have fluency in the basic computer knowledge due to its inclusion in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) subject.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean result of 3.31 is obtained by indicator **google apps**. This finding could be due to the difficulty involved in using the google apps.

The composite mean of 3.65 with its descriptive equivalent of “advanced” tends to imply that, pupils have no difficulties in terms of computer literacy due to familiarization, manipulation, and creation of computer technology. This further tends to indicate that the curriculum included ICT as one of the components in Technology Livelihood Education (TLE) which can be taught by teachers in any grading period help enhance the pupils’ computer literacy.

Table 14

Profile of the Pupils in Terms of Knowledge in Computer Languages

Knowledge Acquired in Science Through Various Materials	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Computer	4.40	0.85	High
Books	3.43	0.75	Fair
Blackboard and chalks	3.63	1.0s5	Fair
Printed page	3.55	0.96	Fair
TV	3.59	1.01	Fair
Composite Mean	3.72	0.50	Fair

Legend:

Scale	Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating
5	4.20 – 5.00	High
4	3.40 – 4.19	Fair
3	2.60 – 3.39	Satisfactory
2	1.80 – 2.59	Low
1	1.00 – 1.79	Beginner

Table 14 displays profile of the pupils in terms of knowledge in computer languages acquired through various means.

As could be gleaned, the table reflects that indicator **computer**, has the highest weighted mean of 4.40, followed by indicator **TV** with 3.59 weighted mean.

On the other hand, indicator **books** gained the lowest weighted mean of 3.43.

The composite mean of 3.72 with its descriptive equivalent as **fair** tends to imply that knowledge acquired in Science through different ways or materials are all described

as “fair”. Evidently, the use of computer which posted high descriptive rating imply that it facilitates the acquisition of knowledge in Science by the pupil respondents.

Table 15

**Level of Efficiency of Computer Assisted Medium of Instruction in Science
in Terms of Functionality**

Functionality	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Consistent CAI-Software with topics/skills found in the DepED Learning Competencies and K to 12 Curriculum Guide in Science.	3.52	1.19	Very Evident
CAI-contributes to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	3.28	1.16	Occasionally Evident
CAI was accurate and congruent to the objectives and subject matter.	3.41	1.19	Very Evident
CAI was updated with the present curriculum.	3.83	0.93	Very Evident
CAI was logically developed and organized.	3.70	0.98	Very Evident
CAI was free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	3.44	1.14	Very Evident
CAI stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	3.81	1.05	Very Evident
CAI was relevant to real-life situations.	3.61	0.98	Very Evident
CAI was appropriate to the target user level of comprehension in terms of language (including vocabulary in Science).	3.41	1.09	Very Evident
CAI promotes positive values that support formative growth.	3.80	0.90	Very Evident
Composite Mean	3.58	0.39	Very Evident

Legend:

Scale	Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating
5	4.20 – 5.00	Highly Evident
4	3.40 – 4.19	Very Evident
3	2.60 – 3.39	Occasionally Evident
2	1.80 – 2.59	Rarely Evident
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not At All

Table 15 displays the level of efficiency of computer assisted medium of instruction in Science in terms of functionality.

As could be gleaned, that table reflects that indicator **CAI was updated with the present curriculum** has the highest weighted mean, followed by **CAI stimulates and promotes critical thinking** with 3.81 weighted mean.

The lowest weighted mean which is 3.28 recorded on **CAI-contributes to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives**.

The result tends to indicate that in technical and technological view of school ICT coordinators, teachers are capable of using computer components, but lacks in maximizing the CAI content in the mastery of identified learning objectives. As indicated, perhaps teachers need to possess the ability to integrate CAI in their lessons due to time constraint and familiarization of technical utilization of computers, as to manipulate and operate the available technology.

Haider and Hussain's study (2014) corroborated with the results of this research who pointed out that teachers must update their content of knowledge and teaching skills

to adjust to the introduction of new curricula, new research findings on teaching and learning changes in the needs of the pupil population, etc.

In addition, Goe and Stickler (2008) refers to professional development that is sustained, aligned with the curriculum, and focused on instruction is shown to positively influence school level achievement.

Table 16

**Level of Efficiency of Computer Assisted Medium of Instruction in Science
in Terms of Adaptability**

Adaptability	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Adapt available technology content materials in Science.	3.81	1.05	Very Evident
Use multimedia-rich games and simulation content to motivate pupils.	3.61	0.98	Very Evident
Encourage pupils to utilize Computer Aided Instruction software in demonstrating manipulative and other representations to explain their Science ideas to each other.	3.65	0.87	Very Evident
Promote collaboration, cooperative learning using CAI-ICT tools.	3.70	0.90	Very Evident
Provide appropriate and varied multimedia content for the diversity of learners.	3.96	1.13	Occasionally Evident
Composite Mean	3.75	0.51	Very Evident

Table 16 displays the level of efficiency of computer assisted medium of instruction in Science in terms of adaptability.

As shown in the table, the indicator **provides appropriate and varied multimedia content for the diversity of learners** has the highest weighted mean of 3.96 followed by indicator **adapt available technology content materials in Science** with weighted mean of 3.81, while **promote collaboration, cooperative learning using CAI-ICT tools** ranked third with weighted mean of 3.70.

The results tend to indicate that adopting integration of CAI can be a great help in developing the methods of teaching and could address the problems pertaining to diverse learners.

Garcia's (2014) statement supported these finding when he claimed that the teachers must use technology as a tool and transform their classroom into interactive, inquisitive learning environment. Schools should be transformed into active learning environments open to their communities. Teachers and pupils must be empowered to be creative agents for change in their schools; and leaders must embrace a vision that prepare their youth for tomorrow's challenges

In the same way, Agyei and Voogt (2011) confirms with the results of this study who inferred that lack of knowledge about ways to integrate ICT-CAI in lessons and lack of training opportunities for ICT integration knowledge acquisition are potential barriers in the success of implementing CAI.

Considering the study of Agyei and Voogt (2011) teachers must be knowledgeable in all aspect of computer literacy.

Table 17

**Level of Efficiency of Computer Assisted Medium of Instruction
in Science in Terms of Usability**

Usability	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Use appropriate CAI-ICT tools to track learner's grades, record attendance and compile reports on student progress.	3.81	1.05	Very Evident
Evaluate pupil's output through distribute and collect feature of Computer Aided Instruction in Science Software	3.61	0.98	Very Evident
Use formative assessment through Computer Aided Instruction in Science	3.48	1.14	Very Evident
Collaborate with the parents on tracking the pupil's progress.	3.69	0.89	Very Evident
Use rubrics in evaluating pupil's output.	3.94	0.88	Very Evident
Use the potential of CAI for online quizzes for ease of access of pupil's results.	4.06	0.98	Very Evident
Transform the formative evidence into a multimedia summative product to publish and share by developing a slideshow and/or video.	3.44	1.19	Very Evident

Provide CAI-content based material as opportunity for both formative and summative assessment purposes.	3.83	0.91	Very Evident
Use electronic portfolio in assessing pupil's performance.	3.54	1.00	Very Evident
Present pupil's progress through MS Excel charts and graphs as representations of and PowerPoint slideshow to ease visualization.	3.70	0.92	Very Evident
Composite Mean	3.71	0.31	Very Evident

Table 17 displays the level of efficiency of computer assisted medium of instruction in Science in terms of usability as assessed by the experts.

As reflected on the table, the highest weighted mean of 4.06 was recorded on indicator **use the potential of CAI for online quizzes for ease of access of pupil's results** next is weighted mean of 3.94 by indicator on **use rubrics in evaluating pupil's output**, and followed by weighted mean of 3.83 by indicator to **provide CAI-content based material as opportunity for both formative and summative assessment purposes**.

The lowest weighted mean which is 3.44 by indicator on **transform the formative evidence into a multimedia summative product to publish and share by developing a slideshow and/or video**.

The composite mean of 3.71 by indicator tends to imply that teachers must continue to elevate and use effective Integration of CAI in science lessons through teacher collaboration. Available online tutorials through video or interactive content can

be a great help for teachers to cope up with the technology in education. Seeking sponsorship of CAI skills training from external stakeholders will be a great help on how to maximize available tools in the classroom.

The findings is corollary to the study of Camacho (2011) which emphasized that along with this effort are the continuous curricular changes and reorientation, teacher training and investment in school facilities and infrastructure, one of which is geared towards the vision of equipping each public school with the modern computer and other information and communication ICT-CAI related programs and instructional materials.

In addition, the study of Ramakrishnan (2016) cited that teacher’s perspective to technology possess a great factor to integrate CAI in teaching. Positive attitude towards new technology could be attributed to the availability, accessibility and knowledge about the use of new technology. This previous study found significant differences in the attitude towards the usage of new technology of teacher with respect to their gender and educational qualification.

Table 18

**Level of Efficiency of Computer Assisted Medium of Instruction in Science
in Terms of Flexibility**

Flexibility	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
CAI was adaptable to different levels of instruction: principles, intermediate, and advanced.	3.81	1.05	Very Evident

Allow freedom of navigation so that the student can return to previous explanations or skip a particular troublesome problem.	3.61	0.98	Very Evident
Give immediate feedback to correct and incorrect answers.	3.89	0.77	Very Evident
Include a help facility to answer pupils questions or provide a reference to the text	4.35	0.68	Highly Evident
The software was easy to use as a blackboard or notebook but provide additional capability including mathematical accuracy, animations, manipulations and rapid calculation	3.39	1.14	Occasionally Evident
Composite Mean	3.81	0.50	Very Evident

Table 18 displays the level of efficiency of computer assisted medium of instruction in Science in terms of flexibility.

As reflected on the table, the highest weighted mean of 4.35 was posted on the indicator **include a help facility to answer pupils' questions or provide a reference to the text**, followed by weighted mean of 3.89 by the indicator **give immediate feedback to correct and incorrect answers**.

The lowest weighted mean of 3.39 was obtained by indicator **the software was easy to use as a blackboard or notebook but provide additional capability including mathematical accuracy, animations, manipulations and rapid calculation**.

The composite mean of 3.81 with its descriptive equivalent of **very evident** tend to imply that, CAI is flexible to use as a tool in teaching Science.

Diviva (2017) revealed the effectiveness of teaching methodologies employed in the classroom. Thus, it is the task of teachers to evaluate persistently the teaching and learning process in science subjects as part of curriculum development and pupils. ' evaluation process. The spectrum of the types of approaches investigated in computer-based science learning has undergone steady change in the last so many years. The largest proportion of research reports involved computer assisted instruction (CAI) and its various modes (tutorials, drill and practice, simulations, instructional games and problem solving).

Table 19

Level of Academic Performance of the Pupils in Science

Range	f	%	Average
91-93	13.0	2.25	85.34
88-90	74.0	12.78	
85-87	358.0	61.83	
82-84	96.0	16.58	
79-81	22.0	3.80	
76-78	16.0	2.76	

Table 19 displays the level of academic performance of the pupils in Science.

As shown on the table, the total number of pupil-respondents who got the highest range of academic performance in Science was 13 or 2.25 percent, followed by 74 or 12.78 respondents.

The average level of academic performance of pupil-respondents in Science was 85.34 which tend to imply that respondents need further interest and enhancement to learn Science using computer assisted instruction.

In addition, the results also imply that the pupil-respondents are obliged to raise up the level of their academic performance in Science. Equally important also is the teachers' effort to assist, inspire and make Science teaching, through CAI, more engaging.

There are still more efforts and time to be invested by the pupil-respondents to further improve their level of academic performance in Science.

The research of Manoucherhi as cited by Hudson (2010) is parallel with the findings of this study who concluded that the lack of computer's use is due to limitations in experiences and access to educational software and support in the use of computers in instruction like CAI.

Table 20

Relationship between the Academic Performance of the Pupils in Science and the Profile of the Teachers

Teachers' Profile		Academic Performance	Remarks
Computer Literacy	Pearson Correlation	.085	Not Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.542	
	Relationship	Negligible	
Competence	Pearson Correlation	-.088	Not Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.527	
	Relationship	Negligible	
Experience	Pearson Correlation	-.006	Not Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.965	
	Relationship	Negligible	

Table 20 shows the relationship between the academic performance of pupils in Science and the profile of the teachers in terms of computer literacy, competence and teaching experience.

Evidently, the results disclosed that the profile of the teachers is not significantly related to the academic performance of the pupils as supported by the p-values (sig) which are all greater than .05. This can be implied that the grades of the pupils in Science were not directly affected by the teachers' profile.

In the local study of Bonifacio (2014) as cited by R.M. Alboro revealed that ICT-CAI can be used to improve the quality of learning. It can promote learners' motivation, mastery of basic concepts and the development of higher order thinking and lifelong learning skills, which fall on the salient features of the K-12 curriculum. The integration

of ICT-CAI helps in the identification of the objectives and targets set by the curriculum. Without the integration of the technology, through the current curriculum, developmental programs would not suffice as to the enhancement of teaching and learning. Motivation, innovation and sustainability of ICT-CAI depend on the kind of leadership that exists. A good leader must be identified in the implementation of these new plans. Of course, resistance could be felt in the air, when new developmental and enhancement programs are integrated in the educational system, this is where the technological leaders must come in. A good leader plan, persuade and perform actions that will allow the different functions to collaborate, share resources and work together to achieve a common goal.

Table 21

**Relationship between the Academic Performance in Science
and the Profile of the Pupils**

Pupils' Profile		Academic Performance	Remarks
Computer literacy	Correlation Coefficient	.089*	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.032	
	Relationship	Negligible	
Knowledge in Computer Languages	Correlation Coefficient	.002	Not Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.956	
	Relationship	Negligible	

**Significant at .05 (2-tailed test)*

Table 21 reveals the relationship between the pupils' academic performance in Science and the profile of the pupils in terms of computer literacy and knowledge in computer languages.

As seen, the computer literacy of the pupils is significantly related with their academic performance having correlation coefficient of .089 significant at .05 level. For a great number of respondents (359 pupils), such a negligible relationship may imply significant relationship. This suggests that computer literacy of the pupils affects their performance in science. The positive correlations show that as the computer literacy of the pupils' increases, their performance in science also increases.

As cited by Tibayan (2009) ICT serves a big help in preparing the lesson in science. It allows creative and unique presentation of the lesson. Teacher can be able to present the lesson easily and helps to present the lesson in a modern way.

On the contrary, knowledge in computer languages is not significantly related with the academic performance in Science.

The difference between computer literacy and knowledge in computer language is that knowledge in computer languages is the ability to access, organize, evaluate and use information from various sources. On the other hand, computer literacy is having the knowledge to use technology in order to manipulate computer software or hardware. Knowledge in computer simply equip pupil-respondents to operate computers while exercising and advancing computer literacy skills can also lead to greater opportunities.

Table 22

Relationship between the Academic Performance of the Pupils in Science and the Level of Efficiency of the Computer Aided Instruction

Level of Efficiency of CAI		Academic Performance in Science	Remarks
Functionality	Correlation Coefficient	.640** (r ² =.41)	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Relationship	Moderately High	
Usability	Correlation Coefficient	.574** (r ² =.329)	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Relationship	Moderate correlation	
Adaptability	Correlation Coefficient	.635** (r ² =.403)	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Relationship	Moderate correlation	
Flexibility	Correlation Coefficient	.629** (r ² =.396)	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Relationship	Moderate correlation	
Efficiency of CAI	Correlation Coefficient	.880 (r ² =.774)	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Relationship	Moderately High	

****Significant at .01 hence significant at .05 (2-tailed test)**

Table 22 reflects the relationship between the academic performance of the pupils in Science and the level of efficiency of the computer aided instruction in terms of functionality, usability, adaptability and flexibility.

Noticeably, all the components of the efficiency of the CAI are significantly related with the academic performance in Science. The most correlated variable is the 'functionality' having a correlation coefficient of .640. The positive correlation implies that as the CAI meets the criteria of a quality equipment, the better is the performance of the pupils. The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = .41$), implies that 41% of the variability of the academic performance can be due to the variability of the 'functionality' of the CAI

As could be gleaned in Table 15, The Level of Efficiency of Computer Assisted Medium of Instruction in Science in Terms of Functionality shows a composite mean of 3.58 with descriptive equivalent of very evident that implies that teachers have the ability to integrate CAI in their lessons due to familiarization of technical utilization of computers as to manipulate and operate the available technology.

Furthermore, adaptability yielded a moderate correlation with the academic performance having correlation coefficient of .635 ($r^2 = .403$). The adaptability of the CAI helped the pupils to learn more science concepts, hence, their performance in Science improved. The coefficient of determination imply that 40.3% of the variability of the academic performance can be explained by the variability of the 'adaptability'

Similarly, 'flexibility' also yielded a moderate correlation with the science performance of the pupils having an r-value of 6.29. This implies that the flexibility of the

CAI gave an easy chance to the pupils to manipulate and discover hidden concepts in science. The coefficient of determination ($r^2=.396$) showed that 39.6% of the variability of the performance of the pupils in science can be due to the 'flexibility' of the CAI.

Finally, the usability of the CAI helped the pupils to perform better as shown by the moderate correlation of .574. This positive correlation shows that 32.9% ($r^2=.329$) of the variability of the pupils' performance in science can be attributed to the usability of the CAI.

Generally, the Computer Aided Instructions yielded a correlation coefficient of .880 with the academic performance of the pupils in science. This moderately high correlation suggest that the use of the CAI showed a direct effect to the performance of the pupil. The coefficient of determination ($r^2=.774$) implied that 77.4% of the variability of the Academic Performance in Science can be explained by the variability of the Computer Aided Instruction.

The results tend to serve as an eye opener to every institution, to explore the potential of using CAI in teaching and learning process. This also further indicate to concerned authority and personnel in charge to conduct more trainings not only to familiarize the teacher-respondents with the software program, but to take the most possible way to utilize CAI.

DISCUSSION

Summary of Findings

1. On profile of teachers' respondents in terms of computer literacy, trainings in computer languages, competence in computer education and experience in teaching Science.

In general, the majority of teacher – respondents along the above-cited competencies were descriptively rated “advanced” based on their respective composite mean.

2. On profile of the pupil – respondents in terms of computer literacy and knowledge acquired in Science

The pupils were disclosed as “advanced” in their computer literacy but “fair” in terms of knowledge in computer languages acquired in Science through various materials such as computer, books, blackboards and chalks and TV.

3. On level of efficiency of CAI in terms of functionality, adaptability, usability and flexibility.

The finding revealed that the level of efficiency of CAI as assessed by experts, were “very evident” in all these mentioned parameters.

4. Majority of the pupil – respondents were recorded to obtain a grade between 85-87. In other words, the academic performance in Science of the pupils is on the average level.

5. The profile of the teachers in terms of computer literacy, trainings in computer languages, competence in computer education and experience in teaching Science were all found not significant to the academic achievements in Science of the pupils.

The profile of the pupils in terms of computer literacy was found significant to their academic performance in Science. However, pupils' profile, in terms of knowledge in computer languages was not significant.

6. The level of efficiency of CAI in terms of functionality, usability, adaptability and flexibility posted significant relationship to the pupils' academic achievement in Science.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The hypothesis that there is no significant relationships between teachers' profile and the pupils' academic achievement in Science is accepted.

The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between pupils' profile and their academic achievement in Science is partially upheld. This is so because only the computer literacy was found to have relationship to the academic achievement of pupils while the knowledge of computer languages did not indicate any relationship.

2. The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the level of efficiency of CAI and the pupils' academic achievements in Science is not accepted.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were drawn.

1. The findings of the study revealed that competency of teacher-respondents in terms of computer literacy, training in computer languages, competence in computer education and experience in teaching Science were descriptively rated "advanced" based on their respective composite mean.

However, much has to be done to raise the bar of teachers' competence, therefore, it is highly recommended that respondents of the study should continue the use of computer literacy knowledge and find ways and means to collaborate with other ICT experts, attend more trainings on computer languages and apply more innovations or digital content in teaching Science to meet the needs of the learners.

On the part of the administrators, it is recommended that they support the needs of the teachers in terms of higher trainings like computer languages to make their own learning materials in a programmed form. They should continue sending teachers more to national and international trainings in other countries with higher computer literacy and most training on computer aided instruction in making CAI modules must be made available to the teachers.

2. The results disclosed that the pupils were “advanced” in their computer literacy but “fair” in terms of knowledge in computer language acquired in Science through various materials, such as books, blackboards & chalks, printed page and TV.

It is therefore recommended to upgrade learning tools in Science with the use of computer, since pupils learned a lot and become well - motivated with the use of computer by providing lessons with games, videos and integrated computer assisted instruction in animated form.

To the administrators, it is humbly recommended that additional computers be added in their plans as one of their top priorities and have it part of their Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses. (MOOE). The assistance and support of some stakeholders and philanthropic organizations can also be solicited to help pupils and teachers avail themselves with computers in Science to be able to achieve the common goal of having quality education and be globally competitive.

3. In as much as the efficiency of CAI in terms of functionality, adoptability, usability and flexibility revealed that the level of efficiency of CAI as assessed by experts, were “very evident” in all these mentioned parameters, it is recommended that curriculum planners and administrators should have an in-depth study of the curriculum to be introduced to the field with proper guidance to teachers how to handle them. Further adequate time must be allotted for the effective implementation of CAI in the curriculum.
4. Since majority of the pupil-respondents were recorded to obtain a grade between 85-87 and were classified to have average level in their academic achievement in

Science, it is recommended that education institutions should include the use of CAI in Science as mandatory part of the curriculum. As to subject offerings and delivery of instructions the pupils should be guided well, by having lessons which are more engaging, interactive and challenging to pupils to increase the level of their academic achievements.

5. The profile of the pupils in terms of computer literacy was found significant to their academic performance in Science. With this finding, it is recommended that the level of computer competency of the teacher-respondents need to be more advanced compared to pupil-respondents' computer literacy. Teacher respondents need to be re-assessed by those who assigned them to find advanced training and give them priority or re-tooling them. The teachers should study more ICT related programs or even indulge themselves to level up more their status in terms of these aspects. The assistance and support of teachers, ICT experts can also be solicited.
6. The level of efficiency of CAI in terms of functionality, usability, adoptability and flexibility posted significant relationship to the pupils' academic achievement in Science. It is recommended that teachers should sustain and maintain the above cited parameters in utilizing CAI as delivery mode in teaching.

Moreover, since the study focused in the use of CAI only in teaching Science, it is recommended that the use of this method be applied in other subject areas to test its effectiveness.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

A. BOOKS

Agyei, Douglas D. Agyei & Voogt Joke, **ICT Use in the Teaching of Mathematics:**

Implications for Professional Development of Pre-Service Teachers in Ghana, Educ Inf Technol (2011) 16:423–439 DOI 10.1007/s10639-010-9141-9, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10639-010-9141-9>, 2011

Friedman & Wyatt, Methods for Correlational Studies, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK481614/>, 2006

Guzel, Ramazan, **Information and Communication Technologies in Schools: A Handbook for Teachers or How ICT Can Create New, Open Learning Environments (Book Review)**, Journal of Foreign Language Education and Technology, 2(1), <http://jflet.com/jflet/index.php/jflet/article/download/43/50>, 2017

Keengwe, Jared Keengwe, Onchwari, Grace & Oigara, James, **Promoting Active Learning**

Through the Flipped Classroom Model. Idea Group, USA, 2014

Krishnaswamy, K. N., Siyakumar, Appa Iyer and Mathirajan, M., **Management Research Methodology: Integration of Principles, Methods and Techniques**, Pearson Education India, retrieved from <https://books.google.com.ph/books?isbn=8177585630>, 2009

Meleisea, Ellie, **ICT in Teacher Education: Case Studies from the Asia-Pacific Region**, UNESCO Office, UNESCO Publication, Bangkok, Thailand, 2008

B. ELECTRONIC REFERENCES

Beale, Vangie. "**What is a programming language?**" en.wikipedia.org, 2016

Camacho, Jose Camacho, Jr. and Pintor, Ranna Maih, **An Analysis of the Effect of ICT Integration in High School Test Performance** in Masbate, Philippines, Osaka University Knowledge Archive: OUKA, <http://ir.library.osaka-u.ac.jp/dspace/>, 2011

Daniel, Case, **Information literacy in a Teacher Education Program** https://scholar.google.com.ph/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&as_vis=1&q=daniels+2012+computer+literacy&btnG=,2012

Department of Science and Technology - Science Education Institute (DOST-SEI), **Evaluation of the Effectiveness of CAI Modules in Mathematics and Science for Intermediate Grade Schools**, www.sei.dost.gov.ph/images/ts/caieval2015.pdf, 2014

Enriquez, Amelito, **Interactive Learning Network (ILN) with Individualized or Group Focus for Real-Time Student Assessment and Assistance**,

<http://www.netsupportsoftware.com/resources/casestudies/files/CaladaCollege.pdf>,

2008

Fleisher, **Integrating Mobile Devices with Learning and Instruction** <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360131515300804>, 2012

Goth, Frohberg C. and Schwabe G., **Mobile Learning Projects – a critical analysis of the state of the art**, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2729.2009.00315>, 2009

Inayat, Ul-Amin R., **Examination of Studies on technology-Assisted Collaborative Learning**, <https://scholar.google.com.ph/scholar?q=Ul-Amin+2010>

Kearsley, Greg & Shneiderman, Ben, **Engagement Theory** An educational philosophy for the cyber-generation. Computers & Education, 1999

Kim, ChanMin and Baylor, Amy L., **A Virtual Change Agent: Motivating Pre-service Teachers to Integrate Technology in Their Future Classrooms**, 2008

Kunkel, Amy, **The Effects of Computer-Assisted Instruction in Reading: A Meta-Analysis**, <https://conservancy.umn.edu/handle/11299/175221>, 2015

Murray, Jacqui, **Technology in the Classroom: What is Digital Literacy**. TeachHUB.com, 2013.

Mercer, Edward, **What Is Computer Based Instruction in Education?** itstillworks.com, 2015

Popoya, Maria, **What Is Science? From Feynman to Sagan to Asimov to Curie, an Omnibus of Definitions**. brainpickings.org, 2012

UNESCO, **Integrating ICT into Teacher Education Curriculum in Asia**, UNESCO

Bangkok Asia and Pacific Regional Bureau for Education,
<http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0022/002235/223520E.pdf>, 2013

UNESCO, **ICT Competency Standards for Teachers, Competency Standards Modules**, <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0015/001562/156207e.pdf>, 2008

Warschauer, Mark, **A Teacher's Place in the Digital Divide**

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-7984.2007.00118>. 2007

Walsh, John, **Computer Assisted Instruction, Methods of instruction in Information**

Literacy, Sciencedirect.com, 2011

C. JOURNALS

Bebell and O'Dwyer. **Integrating Mobile Devices with Learning and Instruction**

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360131515300804>, 2010

Calderon, Jose F., **Methods of Research and Thesis Writing**, reprint, Mandaluyong City: National Bookstore , 2012

Diculen, Ligaya, **Design Development and Summative Evaluation of Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) on Selected Topics in High School Physics**, *ejournal.ph* 2002

Divina, Rachelle C., **Effectiveness of Understanding by Design and Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) in Learning Math**, *ejournal.ph*, 2017

Goe, Laura Goe, Ph.D. and Stickler, Leslie M., **Teacher Quality and Student Achievement: Making the Most of Recent Research**, <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED520769.pdf>, 2008

Haider, Syed Zubair and Hussain, Athar, **Relationship between Teacher Factors and Student Achievement: A Correlational Study of Secondary Schools, US-China Education Review A**, Volume 4, Number 7 (Serial Number 38), retrieved from http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/35831264/US-China_Education_Review_20147A.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAIWOWYYGZ2Y53UL3A&Expires=1489923310&Signature=2uidMFNI8o1rsr2Xrhm1MmSShMg%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DUS-China_Education_Review_2014_7A_.pdf, 2014

Kolb, Alice Y. and Kolb, David A., **Experiential Learning Theory: A Dynamic, Holistic Approach to Management Learning**, Armstrong: Management Learning, Education and Development, page 42-68, Encyclopaedia of the Sciences of Learning- Springer, https://www.researchgate.net/profile/David_Kolb/publication/267974468_Experiential_Learning_Theory_A_Dynamic_Holistic_Approach_to_Management_Learning_Education_and_Development/links/5559122408ae6fd2d826eb12.pdf, 2012

Klein, Hans K. **The Social Construction of Technology: Structural Considerations** Georgia Institute of Technology Daniel Lee Kleinman University of Wisconsin-Madison, Science, Technology, & Human Values, Vol. 27 No. 1, Winter 2002

Mistades, Voltaire, **Cognitive Expectations in Introductory Physics: A Profile of Biology, Liberal Arts and Physics Majors**. ejournal.ph, 2006

Ramakrishnan, Jayalakshmi, **Attitude of Teachers Towards the Usage of New Technology**,

https://www.academia.edu/22849024/ATTITUDE_OF_TEACHERS_TOWARDS_THE_USAGE_OF_NEW_TECHNOLOGY, 2016

Salaria, Neeru, **Meaning of The Term- Descriptive Survey Research Method**, International Journal of Transformations in Business Management, (IJTBM) 2012, Vol. No. 1, Issue No. 6, ISSN: 2231-6868 <http://www.ijtbm.com/>, 2012

D. UNPUBLISHED MATERIALS

Alboro, Richard M., **E – Classroom Utilization, Computer Competency and Content – Based Teaching in the Division of Bataan**, 2017

Awa, Aladin M, **Assessment on Economic Status and the Solid Waste Management**

Practices of the Local Market Vendors of Barangay Poblacion Public Market,

Columbio Sultan Kudarat, Validation Letter for Bachelor Degree Thesis,

<https://www.slideshare.net/aladinawa/validation-letter-for-thesis>, 2012

Dong-Dong, Cui, **A Study of Application of Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) in Wushu Teaching**, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-642-25437-6_76,2012

Konan, Ino, Inonu University, **Education Faculty**, Malatya 44280 Turkey, January 12, 2010

Picciano, A.G., **Definition and Characteristics of Correlational Research**

<https://www.anthonypicciano.com/s8.html>, 2015

Tibayan, **Information and Communication Technology as Aid in Teaching Science in the Public Secondary Schools in the First District of Bataan**, unpublished Master's thesis, Bataan Peninsula State University, Dinalupihan, Bataan, 2009